

THE CONCEPT OF IMAGE IN EDUCATION

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Аннотация. данная статья раскрывает понятие имиджа преподавателя и влияние на образование в высших учебных заведениях.

Ключевые слова: имидж, образование, стратегии, репутация, исследования, перспективы, потенциал, знания.

Abstract. this article reveals the concept of the image of a teacher and the impact on education in higher educational institutions.

Keywords: image, education, strategies, reputation, research, prospects, potential, knowledge.

Annotatsiya. ushbu maqolada o'qituvchining imidji tushunchasi va oliy o'quv yurtlarida ta'limga ta'siri ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tasvir, ta'lim, strategiya, obro', tadqiqot, istiqbol, potentsial, bilim.

Education is one of the spheres of public life, on which the development and potential of society and the country largely depends. It is not only about human capital in the economic sense, but also scientific activity, which is formed through the transfer of knowledge, experience, skills and the desire to learn new things, explore, discover. How valuable it is for a country that has a wonderful cultural heritage and outstanding minds. The reform of one of the elements of the social system, namely education, affects not only the future prospects for the development of this sphere, but also the application by higher education institutions of new strategies in the field of providing educational services, positioning the university. The formation of an effective image of a higher educational institution and its maintenance affects not only the strengthening of positions in the local market of educational services, but also in general allows us to testify about the level of development of education in the region and in the country, which significantly affects the image of education. And although, on the one hand, most state universities have a certain image and reputation, attention is rarely paid to building an image, and this is a mobile system that needs to be developed and maintained, adapted to changing conditions. Any PR campaign begins with a study of problems in a certain area in order to identify the source of negative trends in the company's work. One way or another, not only the problems associated with the lack of image building, effective work with the media, the correct positioning strategy are revealed, but also systemic, organizational problems in the field of process management. A public relations specialist should take into account not only the problems in the field of image, but also the immediate problems existing in the university, in education. The study of these problems will allow us to present the existing picture most clearly and conduct a deep analysis of the situation, which contributes to the selection of tools for the formation of the image of the university. The role of this work is to formulate a number of ideas about the image of the university, contributing to the effective promotion of the university in a competitive environment; to construct a model of interaction between society, the state and the university with the help of public relations. According to the Comcon-2 Eurasia center, 36% of 1,600 respondents are willing to spend a lot of money on educating their children (grandchildren, themselves) and give up a lot. This means that the issue of education is important for Kazakhstanis, as it determines the social status of a citizen in the future. If the consumer has a need for an educational service, the university has the

opportunity to convey information to the consumer in various ways, through various communication channels. For correct positioning, an image with reputation and prestige is necessary. The intensification of work on the image of education, including the image of universities, is seen, first of all, for several reasons. Firstly, the prerequisites are the existing socio-economic problems. For characterization, we quote from the work of V. Slobodchikova: "... education is chronically late, turns out to be in the role of catching up with life itself"[1]. An important trend in the field of education is that universities are starting to work on their image, assessing the level of competition in the market and the increased demand for certain specialties. The work on the image of the university is based on a strategic basis, the situation is assessed not only today, but also in the future. G.G. Pocheptsov characterizes the image as "the most economical way of generating and recognizing complex social reality; as a result of information processing; as a collapsed text; as a communicative unit through which it is possible to work with mass consciousness"[2]. The fundamental difference between branding and image construction is that the first is aimed at forming the consumer habit of buying a certain brand, the second creates a holistic image of the university, and not only services, contributes to the identification of the university and the establishment of harmonious relations, explanatory policy. Nevertheless, the concept of a brand as a symbolic capital, in our opinion, cannot yet be unambiguously imposed on the educational sphere, or at least, if applied, then very carefully. For example, KBTU, KIMEP, KazNU are brands, and UIB or KazEU are only leading universities in the Republic of Kazakhstan. Moreover, this position is somewhat embarrassing, since there is no research work in this direction. To assert something without scientific arguments, in our opinion, is not entirely correct. The trend of using branding captures new areas of social relationships, where it is economically profitable. In other words, where it is necessary to get additional profit, basing its positioning on consumer confidence. When forming an effective image, it is necessary to clearly determine in which direction to work, i.e. to specify which type of image to develop. In this case, it is necessary to understand what elements the image of the university consists of. Determine its structure. Let's consider the structure of the image of the university, complementing it with the ideas that the public has about its elements. N.K. Moiseeva identifies 8 components in the structure of the image of the university. The choice of this approach is due to the fact that it differentiates the structure into elements and allows you to identify the audience's ideas about each component, identify problems and suggest possible adjustments. The limitation of the approach lies in the fact that the image is not immediately considered as a whole, it is differentiated, contradictions may arise between the representations of the image components.

1. The image of an educational service is people's perceptions of the unique characteristics that, in their opinion, the service possesses. Additional services (attributes) are what provide the university with distinctive properties. Ideas: the quality of education, new specialties, specializations, degree after graduation, the cost of services, the level of foreign relations.

2. The image of consumers of educational services includes information about the lifestyle, social status and some personal (psychological) characteristics of consumers. In this case, it is necessary to consider not representations, but the reaction and assessment of consumers regarding the image of the University.

3. The internal image of the organization is the ideas of teachers and students about the university. The main determinants of the internal image are the culture of the organization and the socio-psychological climate. Ideas: the system of spiritual values, the presence of KVN groups

and other creative groups, theater, technological education, innovation, financial stability, the possibility of obtaining a high salary, scholarships.

4. The image of the rector of the university and the scientific council includes ideas about abilities, attitudes, value orientations, psychological characteristics, appearance.

5. The image of the staff is a collective, generalized image of the teaching staff. Representations: professional competence: mobility, accuracy in the performance of official duties, accuracy of work, awareness, professional, highly qualified training; culture: sociability (friendliness in communication, smiling), correctness of speech, socio-psychological characteristics of teachers;

6. The image is formed on the basis of direct contact with a university teacher. At the same time, each employee is considered as a "person" of the university, by which the university as a whole is judged.

7. The social image of the organization is the representation of the general public about the social goals and the role of the university in the economic, social and cultural life of society. Presentations: free education of disabled children by remote technology, orphans, deferral from the army, interaction with other structures of the social system of society, for example, with schools: conclusion of contracts for the admission of medalists, conducting entrance exams at school.

8. The visual image of an organization is an idea of an organization based on visual sensations that capture information about the interior of buildings, lecture halls, and corporate symbols of the organization. Corporate identity is the main component of the tangible image of the university, it is the basis for the development of the philosophy of the university, when creating an internal and personal image. An online representation can also be attributed to the visual image, when a university positions itself using a website.

Public awareness and openness are becoming priorities in the work on the image of the university and the image of its teachers. The main components of the educational paradigm that can be formed are: the quality of education, innovation, prestige, openness. Such an educational paradigm "The Road of Prospects" does not pretend to be universal, it is largely based on the study of the problem and practical observation. But I would like to note the importance of building a paradigm, analyzing and identifying pain points in education today, perhaps to present models for the development of education, our society, our country. All components are interrelated: the teacher's work on the image is an opportunity to increase competitiveness, attract talented applicants who will become qualified specialists in the future, and will work for the development of the state, society, and the country - this is our road to the future.

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